

NATURAL MONUMENTS AND THEIR PROTECTION

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ABSTRACT

This article provides views on natural monuments, their study and protection, in particular, the identification of natural monuments in Bukhara region, the collection of statistical data on them and their protection.

Relevance of the topic: Natural monuments are objects created by nature, which include their preservation, reconstruction, protection of rare trees, plants and others. It is very important today to register trees and use them in tourism. It is necessary to map natural monuments and implement maps. This is not new for the tourism industry, but it remains very shallow.

Goals and objectives: Identification of natural monuments located in Bukhara region

- collection of accurate statistics
- Reduction of negative impacts on the destruction of natural monuments
- Mapping of natural monuments
- Formation of education on the preservation of natural monuments

Natural monuments are unique, remarkable objects created by animate and inanimate nature: caves, waterfalls, beautifully shaped rocks, ravines, geysers, open springs, huge adult trees. Natural monuments are used for scientific, aesthetic, recreational, travel, tourism, recreation, educational purposes. There are more than 400 natural monuments in the country. [Rafiqov, 1997: 124]

Vardondeze Natural Monuments are one of the rare natural monuments under state protection. Originally established as a nature reserve in 1975 in Shafirkan district of Bukhara region, the desert has lost its significance due to the rapid development of the desert and in 1983 was turned into a state natural monument. Vardondeze has a monument. Rare saxaul trees, Richter, Circassian, willow and others grow.

According to the Chorchinor State Natural Monument, the regional department of ecology and environmental protection, there are 213 trees aged 100 and over in Bukhara. Among them is a plane tree in the village of Chorchinor, which belongs to the citizens' assembly of Bohouddin Naqshband mahalla of Kagan district. This maple tree lived for 702 years. According to the legends passed down from generation to generation, the maple sapling was planted by Hazrat Bahauddin Naqshband. There were 4 maples around

the pool. Once upon a time, this road was connected to the western gate of the Bahauddin Naqshband shrine. Now there is only one maple tree left. It is necessary to develop measures to improve the surroundings of the Shar maple complex and turn this natural monument into an ecotourism site, to pay attention to the maple and prevent it from drying out. The age of the plane tree should be written on a special sign. It should be hung as a natural monument. The plane tree should be surrounded by a ribbon.

Karakol monuments. Karakol is located in the south of Uzbekistan, at the confluence of the Kyzylkum and Karakum deserts, in the lower reaches of the Zarafshan River. In ancient times, people lived in Zamonbobo district of Karakol region, Poykent, Kichiktuzkon, Kattatuzkon, Odilkuduk, Kurbanboy, Rahmatbobo, Aqrabod and Hatar. Archaeological finds from the II-I millennium BC include a statue of aya, khovoncha handles, gold beads, precious stones - laurels, various primitive

weapons, copper ornaments. Historically known as the "Modern Culture", it is the culture of the Bronze Age clan, where two semi-basement tents, a pottery kiln and 43 tombs were found. This means that the community was engaged in farming and animal husbandry.

Another ancient monument of Karakol is the city of Poykent (Boykent). Poykent has a history of more than 2,500 years, and its arch and two shahristans are surrounded by a fortified wall. The 20-hectare city is located on an artificial hill.

Outside the city walls, a wide and deep ditch was dug, through which bridges were built. Another historical monument of Karakol, the complex of the mausoleum of Chibirton ota - Shah Abdurahmon Vali, is one of the unique examples of Central Asian architecture. The mausoleum of Shah Abdurahman Vali is built on a high sand hill and consists of two parts: an underground cave and a single domed shrine built on top of it. The shrine has a door on all four sides, and the central roof of the building is decorated with marble, ornaments, and Kufic inscriptions.

The octagonal mausoleum was built in the early 11th century. The appearance of the mausoleum is typical of the Samanid period, with square square bricks, unique construction, compositional structure, elongated dome, and a slightly heavier and taller roof. The mausoleum is not overly decorated on the outside.

The composition of the building is simple: each side is 2.65 meters octagonal, octagonal, covered with a dome 6.4 meters in diameter. A 1.4-meter-diameter hole in the top of the dome served to illuminate the inside of the mausoleum. In addition, the inside of the mausoleum is illuminated by three towers - a fence. The top of the central roof and the bars on the east and south sides are made of terracotta.

Another peculiarity of the mausoleum is that the outer part of the wall of the building, which is 2 meters high, is made of 9 rows of bricks facing outwards. This method was used in Central Asia and Iran in the IX-X centuries to cover the huge columns of monuments made of raw bricks and cotton. Chirirdon ota or Shirburdon ota mausoleum was built in honor of Saint Shirburdon ota during the reign of Amir Temur, in the XIV-XV centuries. The

monument consists of three rooms: a khanaqah, a chillaxona and a gorkhona. The roof of the mausoleum faces the octagonal mausoleum to the east. At the top of the roof there are five cupboards, and in the two corners there are tower-shaped bouquets. The high-domed room of the building is arranged in an octagonal shape on top of the sheets with a spherical dome measuring 10 meters in diameter. The tombs and children's rooms are covered with low domes 4 meters in diameter. The cemetery originally had four doors. The doors on the north and south walls were symmetrical to each other, and the west wall had two doors of the same size. The foundation under the walls of the building is laid in the following order: thick clay is laid on top of a layer of hard sand, two rows of square bricks are laid vertically on top of it, a layer of reeds is laid on top of it and bricks are laid on top of it. During excavations near the building, a set of coins minted in Bukhara in 1428-29 was found. The building resembles the mausoleum of Sayfiddin Boharzi in Bukhara. However, the fact that the roof of the Chibirton ota mausoleum is much lower indicates that it was built in the second half of the 14th century.

The Chibirton ota mausoleum complex was identified in 1951 by the expedition of the well-known archeologist Yahyo Gulyamov. The proposal of the State Committee for Environmental Protection and the Ecological Party of Uzbekistan to declare Lake Urungoch and adjacent areas a state hydrological monument of nature was approved. Ugam-Chatkal State National Park declares the 43-hectare Urungoch Natural Lake and adjacent areas located in the Burchmullo State Forestry Territory as a state hydrological natural monument.

It is noted that the Urungoch State Hydrological Natural Monument is part of the Burchmullo State Forestry and is managed by the farm without confiscation of land and prohibiting any activities that could adversely affect the facility. Chust Natural Monument at the initiative of the Central Asian Plant and Conservation Research Institute

Made in accordance with the decision of the khokimiyat of Namangan region No. 65/5 of 19.08.90 (as well as the decision of the Council of People's Deputies of Chust district of Namangan region No. P-5/12 of August 30, 1990), the area is 1000 hectares.

Natural monument "Yozyavon" formed in accordance with Resolution No. 1842.

The natural monument "Central Fergana" was created in accordance with the decision of the Executive Committee of the Akhunboboev district of the Council of People's Deputies of Fergana region on August 2, 1986 on the land of the farm "Solijonobod" with an area of 142.5 hectares.

The natural monument "Yangibozor" was created in accordance with the decisions of the khokimiyat of Yangibazar district of

Khorezm region (No. 738 of 10.05.03, No. 819 of 4.02.04, No. 853 of 7.08.04, No. 1155 of 17-04.04). The area varied and was 136 ha, 113.2 ha, 120 ha, 121 ha, respectively, and now stands at 490.3 ha.

According to the decision of the Namangan regional khokimiyat No. 164/14 dated 28.12.91, the area of the natural monument "Mingbulak" is 1000 hectares. Formed in accordance with the Resolution No. 65/5 (as well as the Resolution of the Council of People's Deputies of Chust district of Namangan region No. II-5/12 of August 30, 1990), the area is 1000 hectares. The Yazyavon natural monument was built in accordance with the decision of the Fergana regional administration No. 164 of 23.05.94 and covers an area of 1,842 hectares. Natural monument "Central Fergana" In accordance with the decision of the Executive Committee of the Council of People's Deputies of Fergana region Ahunboboev district dated August 2, 1986, the area of the farm "Solijonobod" is 142.5 hectares. district khokimiyat (No. 738 of 10.05.03, No. 819 of 4.02.04, No. 853 of 7.08.04, No. 1155 of 17.04.04). The area varied and was 136 ha, 113.2 ha, 120 ha, 121 ha, respectively. [Norbaeva U., Obidova Sh. Taffakur and Talqin 299]

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